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USE OF DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION

Abstract

Distance learning technologies (DLT) have become an important component of modern higher medical education. They allow students to acquire knowledge regardless of their location, provide access to various educational materials, and contribute to the individualization of the learning process. This article examines the main aspects of using DLT in higher medical education, their advantages and challenges, and the experience of implementing these technologies in different countries.

DLT offer a wide range of methods and tools for education, which enable the organization of the learning process effectively, regardless of the physical presence of students and teachers. There are several ways to classify DLT depending on various aspects of their use.

DLT have significant potential to improve the quality of medical education and ensure access to knowledge for students from different parts of the world. However, for the successful implementation of DLT, it is necessary to overcome technical limitations, ensure proper teacher training, and motivate students to actively participate in the learning process.

The experience of European countries indicates the successful implementation of DLT in higher medical schools. The use of platforms for video lectures, interactive simulations, and hybrid learning models ensures the effectiveness and accessibility of medical education.

DLT are diverse and multifaceted, allowing their use in various contexts and for different educational purposes. The correct choice and integration of DLT can significantly improve the quality of education and make it more accessible to a wide audience of students.

Keywords: distance learning technologies, higher medical education, distance learning.

Introduction

Distance learning technologies (DLT) have become an important component of modern higher medical education. They allow students to acquire knowledge regardless of their location, provide access to various educational materials, and contribute to the individualization of the learning process. This article examines the main aspects of using DLT in higher medical education, their advantages and challenges, and the experience of implementing these technologies in different countries.

Classification of distance learning technologies

DLT offer a wide range of methods and tools for education, which enable the organization of the learning process effectively, regardless of the physical presence of students and teachers. There are several ways to classify DLT depending on various aspects of their use. Below are the main approaches to classifying DLT.

I. By the type of interaction:

1. *Synchronous technologies* – include means that allow simultaneous interaction between students and teachers in real time [1]. Examples: video conferences, webinars, chats, virtual classrooms.

2. *Asynchronous technologies* – allow interaction between students and teachers without the need for simultaneous online presence [1]. Examples: email, fo-

ums, video lectures, electronic courses, learning modules on an LMS (Learning Management System) platform.

II. By the type of content:

1. *Text materials* – e-books, articles, lecture notes, text documents [2].

2. *Multimedia materials* – videos, audio recordings, animations, interactive presentations [2].

3. *Interactive materials* – virtual simulators, interactive laboratories, gamified educational programs [3].

III. By the method of content delivery:

1. *Online learning platforms* – LMS systems like Moodle, Blackboard, Canvas, which provide the integration of all necessary means for distance learning [4].

2. *Web resources and electronic libraries* – websites that offer access to scientific articles, electronic textbooks, educational materials [5].

3. *Mobile applications* – apps for smartphones and tablets that allow access to educational materials and assignments at any time [4].

IV. By the purpose of use:

1. *Formal education* – use of DLT within official educational programs and courses leading to diplomas or certificates [6].

2. *Informal education* – use of DLT for self-study, professional development, or expanding knowledge in

a specific field without obtaining an official document [5].

V. By the level of interactivity:

1. *Low interactivity* – lecture materials that students can view without the need for active participation [3].

2. *Medium interactivity* – quizzes, tests, assignments that require some level of activity and interaction with the material from students [7].

3. *High interactivity* – virtual simulators, role-playing games, group projects that require active participation and interaction with other students and teachers [8].

The classification of DLT provides a comprehensive view of the variety of methods and tools used in distance learning. Each category has its features and can be effectively used depending on the educational goals and context.

Advantages of DLT in Medical Education

1. *Accessibility and flexibility*: One of the main advantages of DLT is the ability to study at any time and from any place. This is especially important for students who cannot regularly attend classes due to geographical or other constraints [9].

2. *Individualization of learning*: DLT allows the adaptation of educational materials to individual student needs, which contributes to more effective knowledge acquisition [10].

3. *Expansion of access to resources*: The use of DLT provides access to a wide range of educational materials, including online libraries, video lectures, simulators, and other digital resources [11].

However, despite many advantages, there are also numerous challenges and issues in the implementation of DLT, including:

1. *Technical limitations*: Poor internet quality or lack of necessary equipment can be obstacles to the effective use of DLT [12].

2. *Insufficient teacher training*: Successful implementation of DLT requires proper teacher training on using new technologies and distance learning methods [13].

3. *Student motivation*: In distance learning, it is important to ensure a sufficient level of student motivation to actively participate in the learning process and complete assignments on time [14].

Experience of implementing DLT in different countries

1. *USA*: In the United States, DLT is actively used in medical schools to increase education accessibility and prepare professionals in remote regions [12].

2. *UK*: In the UK, DLT is used to improve the quality of medical education and ensure access to educational materials for students from different parts of the country [15]. The Open University is a pioneer of distance learning in the UK, offering a wide range of courses, including medical ones. They use video lectures, interactive resources, discussion forums, and student support.

3. *Ukraine*: In Ukraine, the implementation of DLT in medical education has been accelerating, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when traditional learning became impossible [16]. The predominant use of platforms for video lectures and interactive tasks supports the learning process.

4. *Germany*: Use of Moodle and ILIAS platforms to support medical courses in higher education institutions. Focus on interactive simulators and virtual laboratories for medical education [17].

5. *France*: The national platform France Université Numérique (FUN) offers distance courses in medicine for students of medical universities, using MOOCs for broad access to medical knowledge [18].

6. *Sweden*: Medical faculties use video lectures and interactive assignments for distance learning. Preference is given to independent student work using online resources [12].

7. *Spain*: Use of Blackboard platforms and other in-house developments for medical courses. Emphasis on hybrid forms of learning, combining online and offline components [19].

8. *Italy*: Implementation of interactive simulations and virtual patients in the learning process. Student training through interactive platforms and virtual laboratories [20].

Conclusions

DLT have significant potential to improve the quality of medical education and ensure access to knowledge for students from different parts of the world. However, for the successful implementation of DLT, it is necessary to overcome technical limitations, ensure proper teacher training, and motivate students to actively participate in the learning process.

The experience of European countries indicates the successful implementation of DLT in higher medical schools. The use of platforms for video lectures, interactive simulations, and hybrid learning models ensures the effectiveness and accessibility of medical education.

DLT are diverse and multifaceted, allowing their use in various contexts and for different educational purposes. The correct choice and integration of DLT can significantly improve the quality of education and make it more accessible to a wide audience of students.

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